

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF FERTILITY TRAITS BY BIOMOLECULAR MARKERS IN VIGNA SAVI SAMPLES

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Abstract

Vigna Savi, one of the richest genera of the legume family, includes a number of economically important cultivated and wild species. Several marker systems have been applied for genetic mapping, evaluation of genetic diversity, establishment of core collections and screening of resistance to stressors in Vigna species. These include RFLP, RAPD, SCOT, SSR and ISSR markers. Vigna samples selected for superior productivity indicators can be used as a starting form in order to obtain high productivity under irrigation conditions, as well as in selection works in the direction of increasing productivity. Crossing of genetically distant samples as the parental form will allow obtaining valuable recombinants for various traits in the selection process. Bean dimensions (width, length) were also recorded in the plants. The highest indicator is VIG-3 variety and *sps. sesquipedales* sample, the lowest value was recorded in AG-340 sample. The length of the bean varied between 7.5-32.5 cm and the highest result was VIG-3 (32.3 cm) and *sps. sesquipedales* (32.5 cm), and the lowest result was observed in K-1832 (7.5 cm).

Keywords: ISSR, genetics, Vigna, SSR, selection, DNA.

Vigna (*Vigna savi*) genus belongs to beans (*Phaseolinae* Taub) and has more than 57 species, of which 42 species are widespread in Africa. The vast majority of species are annuals. Mainly two species of the genus are cultivated for food and fodder purposes. [1] *V. sinensis* Savi (synonym *V. unguiculata* L.) is an annual plant belonging to the cow pea species and is 20-200 cm tall. The stem is straight or flat, not curling from above. The leaves consist of three compound leaf shapes, and the flower group consists of 2-8 flowers. Its pods are cylindrical and sword-shaped, 7-8 cm long. The size of its seeds varies from small to large (mass of 1000 seeds is 58-370 g). The colors are also different; white, black, light brown to dark brown, green, etc. happens. The species is not found in the wild. It is cultivated commercially in both the tropical and subtropical and favorable regions of the South in the Old and New Worlds (1-3). In the former USSR, these plants are mainly in the South Caucasus and Central Asian republics; and early-growing forms were cultivated in Southern Ukraine, even in the Voronezh region. In Tajikistan, they are also found at an altitude of 2000 m (P.M. Zhukovski, 1967). White forms of the species are widely used, as they are considered to be of better quality as food. Its seeds are rich in lysine, an essential amino acid for human metabolism, and provide 53% carbohydrate, 2% fat, and 22-23% protein (4-7). These seeds differ from other legumes, including beans and chickpeas, due to their high ripening ability. Green beans of vegetable varieties are mainly eaten. Cowpea is also distinguished by its resistance to drought. They are resistant to the dryness of the atmosphere, but despite this, in Central Asia and the South Caucasus, plants need to be watered several times. It is an important component of arid tropical cropping systems such as Asia, the Middle East, Southern Europe, Africa, South America, and Central and South America. It is drought tolerant, which makes it suitable for cultivation in West African savanna and forest savanna zones (2,3,4). People in the South of America use cowpeas or

black-eyed peas as food. From vigna and rice, they prepare an interesting dish called "John's tale" on the New Year holiday.[1] The success of any breeding program depends on the amount of information available about the genetic diversity, structure and potential of the current population. So, where there is no diversity, there is no selection, and genetic improvement of samples is impossible. For the study of genetic polymorphism, morphological signs, biochemical markers, etc. different methods have been used. Several studies have been conducted to characterize genetic variations from cultivated cowpea and its wild progenitors using biochemical, analytical, and molecular marker methods. The purpose of the conducted research is to support the research conducted with morphological and physiological signs. All marker types were used to characterize DNA variation profiles in cultivated cowpea and related wild species. This applies to; allozymes, seed storage proteins, chloroplast DNA polymorphism, RFLP, amplified fragment length polymorphism, random amplified DNA, simple sequence repeats. All these studies have played a great role in the organization of the cowpea genome and the understanding of its evolution. In general, molecular taxonomic studies have been consistent with classification based on taxonomic criteria such as morphological characters. That is, molecular taxonomy is consistent with morphological taxonomy. In addition, these studies are useful for determining duplicate cards and finding genetic contaminants in the genebank and have been used in breeding programs. By manipulating molecular marker technology, several authors have identified a low level of genetic polymorphism in cowpea. The obtained result was attributed to the genetic contraction of cowpea in the process of domestication and, in addition, to the mechanism of self-pollination. During our research, sowing was carried out according to the methodology at a depth of 5-7 cm with 60 cm between rows and 5-10 cm between plants. As a material for sowing, 30 vigna samples were taken (table 1.1).

Table 1.1

Samples of *Vigna* Savi used in the study

№	Kataloq №	№	Kataloq №
1	K – 262	16	VİG – 17
2	K – 252	17	VİG – 36
3	K – 259	18	K – 1190
4	K – 771	19	K – 1138
5	K – 273	20	VİG – 1
6	K – 268	21	VİG – 2
7	K – 263	22	QARA
8	K – 264	23	K – 5390
9	K – 272	24	K – 3480
10	K – 261	25	K – 424
11	K – 267	26	K – 271
12	AG – 342	27	sps. <i>sesquipedalis</i>
13	K – 1832	28	sps. <i>sesquipedalis</i>
14	K – 1292	29	Yerli VİG-3
15	AG – 340	30	Ayla

Samples were comparatively analyzed. During the study, phenological observations were made in the field on the studied planting samples and development phases were recorded. High variability and diversity were observed in *Vigna* genotypes according to the studied productivity elements. The highest variability limit was the number of beans per plant, and the lowest variability limit was recorded for productivity traits from 1 plant. It is known that plant height is one of the most sensitive traits that is affected by the environment and shows a wide range of variation. Plant height is considered a desirable trait for breeding, as tall plants have a high number of pods and thus exhibit high yields. Taller plants also make it a bit easier to harvest with a combine harvester. In the collection we studied, the height of the plants varied from 20 to 135 cm. In addition, K-261, VIG-36, K-1190, VIG-3, sps. *sesquipedalis* variety is also distinguished by its high height (110-135 cm). As mentioned, the number of beans in 1 plant changed in a wide interval (85), on average 11.8 beans were obtained from one plant. K- 262, K- 252, sps. *sesquipedalis*, examples can be shown. Bean dimensions (width, length) were also recorded in the plants. The width of the bean varied between 0.5-1 cm.

The highest indicator was VIG-3 variety and sps. *sesquipedales* sample, the lowest value was recorded in AG-340 sample. The length of the bean varied between 7.5-32.5 cm and the highest result was VIG-3 (32.3 cm) and sps. *sesquipedales* (32.5 cm), and the lowest result was observed in K-1832 (7.5 cm).

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